

SHORT NOTES

Fluorescence Emission Spectra and Structure of Humic and Fulvic Acids

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Soil humic and fulvic acids are known to fluoresce both under visible and UV light, a property which many investigators¹⁻⁷ utilised in the observation of the progress of their fractionation by chromatographic methods. A quantitative study of this property and spectral distribution of fluorescence colour has not, however, been made so far. The present note reports a study of the spectral distribution of fluorescence colour of soil humic, humatomelanolic, and fulvic acids, a discussion on the skeletal structure of the fluorophore responsible for the observed fluorescence, and fluorescence properties of synthetic humic and fulvic acid-like substances⁸, prepared separately from catechol, hydroquinone, and glucose.

Procedure.—Fluorescence measurement was made in a Beckman DU spectrophotometer provided with a spectral fluorescence attachment where front-surface illumination was employed. The exciting radiation (365 m μ) was obtained from the mercury-vapour lamp. The sample was taken in a 1 cm silica cell. The reference glass was set at 530 m μ with 100 on the % transmission scale at a slit width of 0.14 mm. The fluorescent radiation at different wave lengths was recorded in terms of the percentage scale reading.

Humus from surface layer of a sample of black cotton soil (Padegaon, Bombay) was extracted with 0.5*N*-Na₂CO₃. The extract was treated with HCl to bring the pH to 2.0-3.0 whereby 'crude' humic acid was precipitated. The precipitate was redissolved in Na₂CO₃, reprecipitated, and separated from the supernatant liquid in the centrifuge. The process was repeated thrice and the 'crude' humic acid was finally electro-dialysed to remove electrolytes. A portion of the dried 'crude' humic acid was fractionated into ethanol-soluble humatomelanolic and ethanol-insoluble humic acid, which were converted into their H-forms by electro-dialysis. The yellow supernatant liquid in the centrifuge is the so-called fulvic acid. This was fractionated into fulvic acid 'B' and 'D' by Forsyth's technique⁹. A portion of fulvic acid could be extracted with *n*-butanol. The butanol layer was separated and dried under an infrared lamp. The dried material was dissolved into water-saturated *n*-butanol

1. Hock, *Boedenk. Pfl. Ernähr.*, 1937, 5, 1.
2. Kononova *et al.*, *Pochvovedenie*, 1953, No. 3, 83.
3. Pavel *et al.*, *Ann. Acad. tchecosl. Agric.*, 1953, 26A, 155.
4. Waldron and Mortensen, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1961, 25, 29.
5. Kononova and Titova, *Pochvovedenie*, 1961, No. 11, 81.
6. Coulson *et al.*, *J. Soil Sci.*, 1959, 10, 271.
7. Sowden and Deuel, *Soil Sci.*, 1961, 91, 44.
8. Coulson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, 88, 191.
9. *Biochem. J.*, 1947, 41, 176.

and freed of any insoluble residue by centrifugation. The humic, hymatomelanic, and fulvic acids were converted into their sodium salts for measurement of their fluorescence spectra. The results are graphically presented in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1. Fluorescence emission spectra.

L.H. ordinate: Crude humic acid (O, 20 mg./100 ml, pH=7.53); humic acid (—o—, 20 mg./100 ml, pH=7.20); hymatomelanic acid (Δ , 20mg./100 ml, pH=7.20); fulvic acid 'B' fraction ($\bullet$, in ethanol, concentration not determined).
 R.H. ordinate: Fulvic acid 'D' fraction ($\blacksquare$, 14.4 mg./100 ml, pH=5.46); butanol-extracted fulvic acid ($\square$, 79 mg./100 ml in water-saturated *n*-butanol).
 Curves denoted by O, —o—, Δ , and $\square$ refer to slit width of 0.86 mm; $\blacksquare$, $\bullet$ by 1 mm and $\bullet$ by 0.5 mm.

Humic and fulvic acids exhibit nearly similar, green, feeble fluorescence with more or less flat maxima in the region of 500-540 $m\mu$. It appears probable therefore that fulvic, hymatomelanic, and humic acids are not dissimilar groups of compounds but represent a sequence of polymers. Several factors, namely, the orientation of the functional groups (these contain both fluorescence-activating and inhibiting groups), partially flexible nature of the molecules, molecular crowding, and absorption of a part of the emitted radiation by the absorbing centres in them, all contributing to their low fluorescence yield. Under comparable concentrations, fluorescence decreases in the order: hymatomelanic acid > crude humic acid > humic acid, owing possibly to the presence in them of the fluorophore group in decreasing concentrations. Alternatively, it may be assumed that the structure of hymatomelanic acid is more compact than humic acid, a somewhat flexible skeleton of which inhibits fluorescence. Although the exact characterisation of the relevant fluorophore group is not possible from the present study, fluorescence¹⁰ itself suggests the presence

10. Bowman *et al.*, *Science*, 1955, 122, 32.

of either (a) an aromatic nucleus, substituted by at least one electron-donating group, or (b) a conjugated unsaturated system, capable of high degree of resonance. The former view is supported by isolation¹¹⁻¹² of a number of aromatic compounds from the oxidative degradation products of humic acids. Some of these aromatic compounds, which are mostly polyphenols, phenolic aldehydes, and acids, are known to fluoresce under UV light, a fact which is strongly in support of the presence of similar, though not identical, moieties in the skeleton of humic acid molecule. The presence of a condensed ring structure in humic acid has long been postulated¹³.

Synthetic humic and fulvic acids fluoresce much less than their soil counterparts. Their emission bands (not shown in Fig. 1) lie at shorter wave lengths.

Thanks of the authors are due to Dr. (Miss) K. K. Rohatgi, now Assistant Professor of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur, for lending the use of the spectrophotometer, and to Messrs G. S. Singhal and P. Bhattacharya, Research Scholars, Jadavpur University, for their co-operation.

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Received November 4, 1963.

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